

TEACHING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS TO THINK INDEPENDENTLY BASED ON THE COMPETENT APPROACH

Abdirashidova Maftuna Ilhomovna,

Master of Pedagogical Institute of Termiz State University

Scientific advisor: **Azimova Dilfuza Usmanovna**

Annotation: *In the article, teaching elementary school students to think independently on the basis of a competency-based approach, independent thinking as a way of perceiving reality, is the product of the process of thinking - the highest result.*

Keywords: *competence, independent thinking, education, interactive methods, practical content.*

It can be seen that it is necessary to identify advanced methods of developing independent thinking skills in the process of teaching the native language of elementary school students, to develop factors that influence it, and to recommend the results of experiments and tests. is the main goal of the research. about the problem for practice. In determining the efficiency of the developed system, scientific and methodical experiences, proposed ideas, methodological recommendations, conclusions made through educational technologies are of great importance.

The renewal of education based on the competence approach does not mean giving new knowledge to teach students to think independently, but also envisages changing the system of attitudes towards society, the state, nature and work.

As stated in the Law "On Education" [1], in a democratic society it is necessary to educate a person to think freely and independently.

The method of scientific research was used to determine the level of independent thinking of elementary school students. In this case, mother tongue lessons were observed in general education schools from primary classes to control

and experimental classes. Also, an interview was conducted with elementary school students and elementary school students, and an attempt was made to determine the level of independent thinking of elementary school students based on questionnaires and questions.

Preparation for the implementation of the problem-based learning methodology in the native language classes of primary grades is carried out in the following stages [4]:

- creating a problematic situation regarding the educational material during the lesson;
- directing a problematic situation to a specific goal according to the content of the lesson topic.

This schematic plan of problem-based lesson organization is fully or partially implemented in elementary grades and depending on one or another educational problem. The problematic situations that arise in this place have their own characteristics. Some of them require first to analyze conclusions, concepts, laws and theory for their solutions, others require summarization of facts, still others rely more on comparison of phenomena, concepts, etc. [5]

Scientific research work was carried out in schools 1 in the city of Termiz, 3 and 6 in Sherabad district.

Only 8 elementary school students and 250 elementary school students participated in the science experiment. 50 of them are in the 1st grade, 58 are in the 2nd grade, 52 are in the 3rd grade, and 40 are in the 4th grade.

In the process of scientific research, scientific research methods such as interview, question-and-answer, observation, experiment and questionnaire were used.

Observations were conducted from the beginning of the school year in grades 2-4, and from October after the end of the pre-alphabetic period in grades 1.

At the beginning of the trial, 43 hours of classes were observed at the beginning of the 2021-2022 academic year. The following responses were received to the questionnaire distributed about the period of teaching independent thinking to primary school students:

1. From preschool age - 11 people
2. - 13 people from primary classes
3. -28 people from the upper class

It can be seen that most elementary school students believe that independent thinking of elementary school students mainly begins in the upper grades. Naturally, this negatively affects the process of independent thinking.

The answers of elementary school students to the question about the method of teaching independent thinking were as follows.

Method of searching for problems - 8

Independent works - 12

Didactic games - 9

Free communication between a primary school student and a student - 13

6 elementary school students indicated the need to use all the methods mentioned above, 4 elementary school students indicated the use of oral teaching methods.

Most (27) elementary school students emphasized the need to provide favorable conditions for students' independent thinking process. At the same time, 31 elementary school students asked for instructions on how to conduct independent work. Also, elementary school students reported that elementary school students are shy when communicating with elementary school students (29 people) and that elementary school students strictly control every move (23 people). they emphasized. It is clear from these answers that the conditions for independent thinking of elementary school students are not created in the educational process.

The method of problem-based research in native language classes serves as an important tool in improving students' oral and written speech, literacy level, and teaching them to think independently [2].

The analysis of the results of the questionnaires conducted with primary school students showed that the insufficient development of the system of teaching independent thinking in the process of teaching the mother tongue has a negative impact on the thinking of primary school students. is doing.

In teaching independent thinking, elementary school students use independent works, didactic games and only some educational methods. While the educational process is boring for primary school students, it does not allow them to think independently. In the first phase of the experiment, the 31 lessons we observed were traditional lessons, using only conversation, story, and question-and-answer methods. Only a few forms of didactic games were touched upon in 16 hours of observation lessons. In the 12-hour class, handouts and independent work such as test tasks were used.

The lack of preparation of elementary school students, the monotony of lessons affected the level of independent thinking of elementary school students. We witnessed this in the process of determining the level of independent thinking of elementary school students.

Based on the interview, we tried to determine the level of independent thinking of 1st grade primary school students. For this purpose, the 1st grade elementary school students were given the task of creating an independent story using 5 types of pictures depicting nature scenes in different seasons, people's work in the fields and gardens. At the initial stage of learning, almost all students asked for help from a primary school student. According to the results of observation, the thinking of primary school students was evaluated in the following 3 stages:

High level. They included primary school students who could write a story of 4-5 sentences based on the instructions of a primary school student. Special attention was paid to the logical connection of sentences and the use of words in their place in their stories (58 primary school students).

Average level. These include elementary school students who can compose a 1-2 sentence story with the help of an elementary school student. Among them, 1-2 errors were noted (94 students).

lower level. It includes stories of elementary school students who made logically unrelated and grammatical errors with the direct help of an elementary school student (50 elementary school students).

58 students from the control class, 52 students from the experimental class, a total of 50 primary school students of the 1st grade took part in the interview. The results of the first phase of the experiment were as follows:

Considering that 1st grade primary school students entered school in the initial period of the experiment, it is not necessary to forget whether they went to kindergarten or not. As it turned out, 37 students with high grades, 50 with average grades, and 43 with low grades went to kindergarten. It follows from this that the constant communication and daily activities of kindergarten students with primary school students and peers are important in the formation of children's speech, vocabulary, self-confidence and independence.

With these results, we do not mean that the children were not raised well at home. At home, parents give their children a good education, but it should not be overlooked that special education is not organized to prepare them for school and increase vocabulary. It is no secret that the interest of children brought up in the family to natural phenomena and its changes is not fully satisfied, and the conditions for independent thinking are not provided.

Based on the primary school curriculum and educational standards, we tried to determine the level of independent thinking of primary school students through

test tasks from the textbook. 3 points for each correct and clear, creative answer, 2 points for unclear and unusual answers in open tests, 1 point for incomplete answers in open tests, 0 for incorrect answers in closed tests score and all are recorded.

2-3-4 grade test questions were also aimed at determining their level of independent thinking in the first stage. The test tasks were determined in order to determine the level of independent ability of elementary school students to independently solve tasks other than textbook assignments without the help of an elementary school student. 58 students from the 2nd grade, 52 from the 3rd grade, 40 from the 4th grade took part in the test survey, and the results are as follows:

As a result of the experiment, it became clear that the independent thinking of elementary school students is not up to the required level. In order to determine the reasons for this situation, in the first stage of the experiment, 10 hours of lessons were observed in the 1st grade, 9 hours in the 2nd grade, 11 hours in the 3rd grade, and 13 hours in the 4th grade. class All of these lessons are traditional, using questions and answers, exercises, conversations, storytelling techniques and handouts. However, in these lessons, no importance is attached to the development of independent, creative thinking skills of elementary school students.

In the observed lessons, they did not use the method of problem identification. At least elementary students should ask: "Why?", "What do you think?", "What is your opinion?". no such questions were asked. In the lessons, work was carried out only with the opinion of elementary school students. There is no "subject-subject" relationship between primary school pupils and students. Student activity was not observed in the lesson. The level of creativity of primary school students cannot meet the demand. They are used to passing the lesson only in one sample.

In experimental classes, an attempt was made to determine the level of independent thinking of elementary school students through a game based on puzzles. To do this, the elementary student asks elementary students for 3 riddles

or the same definition. Students write "Question 1" on their answer sheets. At the bottom, they write "Answer 1", "Answer 2", "Answer 3", and after reading each puzzle (definition), they write the answers on the answer sheet. The first puzzle (definition) is difficult, the second (definition) is easy, and the third puzzle (definition) is very easy. Intelligent elementary students who can think independently find the correct answer to the first puzzle and eventually recognize that all three answers are the same. This standard allows for more realistic results and facilitates evaluation. That is, if the correct answer is found in the first puzzle (definition), 3 points, if the correct answer is found in the second puzzle (definition), 2 points, if the correct answer is found at the end . 1 point is awarded only on the third attempt. 0 points if no correct answer is found.

During the experiment, students were asked 10 puzzle questions (Appendix 5) and independent thinking skills of elementary school students were determined at three levels:

High level: students who scored 21-30 points.

Intermediate level: students with 11-20 points.

lower level: students with a score of 10 or less.

Based on this criterion, the results are as follows:

As can be seen from the results, favorable conditions for independent thinking of elementary school students are not provided during the educational process.

In primary grades, the task of the elementary school student is not only to form reading skills and provide basic information in the mother tongue, but also to develop the ability of independent thinking of elementary school students.

After studying the lessons and work experience of elementary school students, and observing the ability to work on textbook materials and the level of independent work of elementary school students graduating from elementary school, we came to the conclusion that elementary school o Primary school students do not pay much attention to lessons. to prepare elementary school

students. creative works of elementary school students, didactic games and various forms of independent work are not used in the course of the lesson, independent intellectual activity of elementary school students is not sufficiently organized from educational materials. As a result, an elementary school student who does not have the ability to work on the textbook moves to higher grades. This, on the one hand, prevents the primary class from improving the student's knowledge, and on the other hand, has a negative effect on the mastery of higher classes. As a result, primary school students are unable to meet current state educational standards and requirements after graduation.

Based on the above, we tried to create an independent educational system in the native language class of primary classes.

References

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining «Ta'lim to'g'risida»gi Qonuni, "Xalq so'zi", 2020 yil 24 sentyabr, 202 (7704)-son.
2. Hasanova A. O'quvchi yoshlar tarbiyasida rag'batlantirish va tanbeh mezoni. – T.: «O'zbekiston», 1996.
3. Nazarova H.P. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ savodxonligini ta'minlashning didaktik asoslari. Monografiya. - T.: 1999. –245 b.
4. Toirov G'. Ona tilidan mashq bajarish jarayonida o'quvchilarning bilish faolligini oshirish. Toshkent, 1991. 193 b.
5. Azimov Y.Y., Qo'ldoshev R.A.. Husnixatga o'rgatishning amaliy asoslari (Metodik qo'llanma) GlobeEdit, 2020, -130 b.
6. O'zbekiston Respublikasining «Ta'lim to'g'risida»gi Qonuni, "Xalq so'zi", 2020 yil 24 sentyabr, 202 (7704)-son.
7. Hasanova A. O'quvchi yoshlar tarbiyasida rag'batlantirish va tanbeh mezoni. – T.: «O'zbekiston», 1996.
8. Nazarova H.P. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ savodxonligini ta'minlashning didaktik asoslari. Monografiya. - T.: 1999. –245 b.

9. Toirov G'. Ona tilidan mashq bajarish jarayonida o'quvchilarning bilish faolligini oshirish. Toshkent, 1991. 193 b.
10. Azimov Y.Y., Qo'ldoshev R.A.. Husnixatga o'rgatishning amaliy asoslari (Metodik qo'llanma) GlobeEdit, 2020, -130 b.
11. SI Tursunova. "Uzbekistan is a country of friendship" Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. 185-189
12. Tursunova Saida Isakovna, O'rolova Ro'zigul Yo'lchi."Yosh avlodni voyaga yetkazishda tarbiyaning ahamiyati" PEDAGOGS jurnali. 15-22. 2022/12/15
13. Tursunova Saida Isakovna."Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatini shakllantirish" PEDAGOGS jurnali. 179-185. 2022/12/15
14. Tursunova Saida Isakovna "Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ilmiy dunyoqarashini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari" PEDAGOGS jurnali. 172-178. 2022/12/15
15. Tursunova Saida Isakovna, Mustafayeva Nigora Xaydarovna. "Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini tarbiyalashda mehnat tarbiyasining ahamiyati" PEDAGOGS jurnali. 186-191. 2022/12/15
16. Toshpulatova Niyokhon Shavkatjonovna// A Creative Approach to Teaching Geometry in the Primary Grades//International Journal on Orange Technologies//48-53-bet
17. Shabbazova, D. (2022). CONTENT OF FACTORS DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(5), 630-636.
18. D Azimova "The main Peculiarities of web tool 2 during teaching" Academic research in educational sciences, 2021.
19. Parvina Kholikova Abdumalik kizi. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE AND PLACE OF USING NATIONAL VALUES IN THE EDUCATION OF THE YOUNG GENERATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal,

<https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/2793>Parvina

Kholikova Abdumalik kizi. (2022).

20. Оллокулова, Ф. (2022). Социально-педагогическое значение формирования научно-исследовательской деятельности учеников начальных классов на основе концентризма. Общество и инновации, 3(10/S), 128–134. <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol3-iss10/S-pp128-134>

21. Muminova Umida Karshievna INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE “TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE ” Ankara, Turkey 2023 46 PHYTONYMS IN THE WORK "MAHBUB UL -QULUB".

22. Shabbazova, D., Abduhalimova, Y., & Abdunazarova, Z. (2022). Psychological And Pedagogical Factors Of Developing Literacy Of Primary Class Students Based On Personal Value Approach. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 6(9), 3707-3712.

23. Dilfuza Shabbazova. (2022). MODEL OF PERSONAL VALUE FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL LITERACY LESSONS. European Scholar Journal, 3(5), 80-83. Retrieved from

24. R.Norqobilova, M.To'rayeva Importance of talent in child development. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, VOLUME 3, ISSUE 7, July. 2022 57-61.

25. R.D.Norqobilova. “Methods of improving the mechanisms of diagnosing the mother language ability of primary class students”. The role of science and innovation in the modern world. 139-143. 2022

26. R.D.Norqobilova. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari faoliyatini indikatorlar asosida diagnostika qilishning o'ziga xosligi. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 564-568. 2023

27. RD Norqobilova. USE of diagnostic tests in foreign schools. Results of National Scientific Research International Journal. 359-364. 2023.
28. R.Norqobilova, S.Ibrohimova.”Pedagogical and psychological factors of using the heritage of Asian thinkers in the formation of ecological thinking in primary school science classes”. European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA). Available Online at: <https://www.scholarzest.com> .Vol. 3 No. 06, June 2022. ISSN: 2660-5589
29. D.U. Azimova “Abdullah Avloni’s Pedagogical Wiefs and its Essence” The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. 2021.
30. D.A. Usmanovna “Psychological problems of children and methods of solution” Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 2022.
31. A.Dilfuza “Boshlag’ich ta’limda aksiologik yondashuv”. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 2022
32. D.U.Azimova. On the Example of Abdulla Avloni, The Hero of the National Awakening Period. MIDDLE EUROPEAN 179 SCIEARCH BULLETIN. 2022, [177/180] ISSN 2694-9970